

SUMMARY OF LOGISTICS PROCESS MANAGEMENT OF CONTEMPORARY AUTOMOBILE ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

The contemporary automobile industry is developing rapidly and the competition is fierce. The logistics process management of automobile enterprises plays a decisive role in the fate of enterprises. This study deeply analyzes the current situation of logistics process management in contemporary automobile enterprises, and reveals the problems and development trends. From the perspective of logistics link integration, technology innovation integration and supply chain strategic coordination, this research studies the three key logistics links of supply, production and sales, and uses various methods such as field research method, data analysis method and comparative research method. This study multidimensional, and methods to explore the contemporary automobile enterprise logistics process management, comprehensive analysis the core points and optimization path, for the automobile enterprise in logistics management innovation, cost control and market competitiveness provides valuable decision-making basis and practice guide, power car enterprises in global competition steady development and occupy a favorable market position.

Keywords: automobile enterprise; logistics process management; supply logistics; production logistics; sales logistics; logistics optimization method.

INTRODUCTION

Introduction: In the context of the accelerated globalization process, the automobile industry, as one of the important pillars of the manufacturing industry, is experiencing unprecedented rapid development and fierce competition. With the increasing diversification of consumer demand, the rapid development of technological innovation and the dynamic evolution of the market pattern, automobile enterprises are facing many challenges and opportunities. In this complex industrial environment, logistics process management gradually comes to the forefront and becomes one of the key factors for automobile enterprises to stand out in the competition.

The logistics process of automobile enterprises runs through the whole process from parts procurement and supply, material circulation in the manufacturing process, to the final product sales and delivery to customers. Efficient and optimized logistics process management can ensure the timely supply of parts, avoid production interruption due to material shortage, and improve production efficiency and resource utilization. At the sales end, it can ensure the rapid and accurate delivery of automobile products to customers, and improve customer satisfaction and loyalty. On the contrary, if there are defects and bottlenecks in the logistics process, it may lead to serious consequences such as sharp cost rise, delivery delay, customer loss and so on, which will threaten the survival and development of enterprises.

In recent years, the continuous innovation of logistics technology, such as the Internet of Things, big data, artificial intelligence and other emerging technologies in the field of logistics, has brought new opportunities for the logistics process management of automobile enterprises. At the same time, the deepening of the supply chain management concept also urges the automobile enterprises to pay more attention to the strategic

coordination with suppliers and partners, so as to realize the efficient operation of the whole supply chain. In this context, it is of great theoretical and practical significance to deeply study the logistics process management of contemporary automobile enterprises.

This study aims to comprehensively and deeply analyze the current situation of logistics process management in contemporary automobile enterprises, explore the existing problems, and explore the future development trend. Through the logistics link integration, technology innovation and supply chain strategy synergy unique perspective, for supply, production, sales and other key logistics link and its cohesion meticulous research, and using field research method into enterprise line to obtain real data and case, with the law behind the data analysis and the relationship, using the mining data comparative research method for the successful experience and failure lessons of different enterprises, and multidimensional, many methods to reveal the core of automobile enterprise logistics process management and optimization path. Expect this research results for automobile enterprises in logistics management innovation, cost control and market competitiveness to provide feasible decision basis and operational practice guide, power automobile enterprises in the tide of global competition, firmly occupy a favorable market position, achieve the long-term goal of sustainable development.

1. Enterprise research status

The global auto industry today is now undergoing profound changes. On the one hand, the competition in the traditional fuel vehicle market is becoming more and more fierce, and the market saturation is gradually rising. The major automobile manufacturers are engaged in all-round competition in brand building, technology research and development, cost control and other aspects. On the other hand, the new energy vehicle market has emerged as a new force, with its envi-

ronmental protection and other advantages, energy saving has attracted many consumers and investors, become a new growth point of the automobile industry, and promote the traditional car enterprises to accelerate the transformation and layout. At the same time, the automobile consumer market presents diversified and per-

sonalized demand characteristics, and consumers requirements for the quality, intelligent configuration, after-sales service and other aspects of automobiles are constantly improving, which poses higher challenges to the flexibility and accuracy of the production and logistics distribution of automobile enterprises.

Table 1

Growth trend of automobile market size

a particular year	Global car sales (ten thousand units)	Sales volume of new energy vehicles (ten thousand units)	New energy vehicle market share
2019	9563	201	2.1%
2020	9129	221	2.4%
2021	7797	324	4.2%
2022	8268	649	7.8%
2023	8105	1009	12.5%
2024	8350 (Estimated)	1500 (expected)	18.0% (expected)

In such an industrial pattern, the logistics process management of automobile enterprises has become an important part of the core competitiveness of enterprises. Efficient logistics process can effectively integrate supply chain resources, timely obtain high-quality parts from the global component suppliers, and ensure the continuity and stability of production. In the production process, accurate material distribution and circulation management can reduce the inventory backlog and waste on the production line, and improve the production efficiency and product quality. At the sales end, fast and reliable logistics distribution can make automobile products quickly reach consumers quickly, improve customer satisfaction and brand image, and then promote the growth of sales performance. On the contrary, if the logistics process is poorly managed, it may lead to a series of problems such as supply chain fracture, production delay and customer complaints, which will seriously affect the economic benefit and market position of enterprises.

2. literature review

With the acceleration of the globalization process of the automobile industry and the increasingly fierce market competition, the importance of logistics process management in the automobile enterprises has become more and more prominent. Many scholars have conducted in-depth research on the logistics process management of automobile enterprises from different perspectives, and these research results provide a rich theoretical basis and practical experience reference for the further analysis of the logistics process management of contemporary automobile enterprises.

The early concept of logistics mainly focused on the physical transportation and storage of materials. With the development of economy and technology, it gradually expanded to the integrated management concept covering the whole link of procurement, production and sales. The rise of supply chain management theory provides a macro strategic framework for the logistics process management of automobile enterprises, emphasizing the collaborative cooperation and resource integration among enterprises. Christopher (Christopher), for example, in his book, logistics and supply chain management, supply chain management is through the feedforward information flow and feedback

of material flow and information flow, suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers until the end users into a whole management mode, this theory for auto enterprises to build a complete logistics supply chain system provides the guiding ideology of [1].

In terms of supply logistics, scholars focus on key areas such as supplier management, procurement strategy and component supply coordination. Studies have shown that the establishment of long-term, stable and close strategic partnership between automobile companies and suppliers is crucial to ensure the stability and quality of parts supply. For example, Mentzer and other scholars have found through empirical research that effective supplier relationship management can reduce the procurement cost, shorten the supply cycle and improve the reliability of supply [2]. In addition, the on-time procurement (JIT) strategy is widely used in the supply logistics of automobile enterprises. As a successful model of JIT procurement, Toyota Motor Corporation has realized the "zero inventory" supply mode of parts through close cooperation with suppliers, which greatly improves the production efficiency and capital turnover rate. Related studies further explored the conditions and challenges of JIT procurement implementation, including the influence of the geographical location of suppliers, production capacity flexibility and the degree of information sharing on their effects [3].

The research on production logistics mainly focuses on the distribution and circulation optimization of materials on the production line. The concept of lean production occupies a core position in the production and logistics of automobile enterprises, which advocates maximizing the production efficiency by eliminating waste and optimizing the process. As an important tool for lean production, Kanban management plays a key role in material distribution control. Scholars have studied the calculation of the number of kanban, the transfer mechanism of the kanban and the matching with the production line beat. For example, in its research on Toyotas production mode, Ohno Taiichi elaborated how kanban management can the "pull" distribution of materials to ensure the timely supply of materials on the production line. In addition, the application of automatic material handling technology in automobile production and logistics has also attracted much

attention. The introduction of industrial robots, automatic guide vehicles (AGV) and other equipment improves the efficiency and accuracy of material handling, and reduces the labor cost and labor intensity. Related research discusses how to reasonably plan the layout and operation parameters of the automatic material handling system to achieve seamless connection with the production process [4].

The research of sales logistics focuses on logistics distribution network optimization, customer delivery experience improvement and logistics cost control. With the rise of e-commerce, automobile sales channels show a trend of diversified development, which puts forward higher requirements for sales logistics. Scholars have used operational research methods to optimize logistics distribution routes to reduce transportation costs and improve distribution efficiency. For example, the vehicle path problem (VRP) model proposed by Dantzig and Ramser and its subsequent improved versions are widely used in automobile sales logistics distribution route planning. At the same time, in order to improve the customer delivery experience, enterprises pay attention to the real-time tracking and feedback of logistics information, so that customers can understand the transportation status of automobile products at any time. In terms of logistics cost control, the research found that the integration of third-party logistics resources and the adoption of joint distribution modes can effectively reduce the sales logistics cost [5].

3. Challenges of logistics process management of automobile enterprises

Supply chain complexity: The supply chain of automobile enterprises covers a large number of parts suppliers, distributed in different parts of the world. There are differences in their production capacity, supply stability, and quality standards, which increases the

difficulty and risk of supply chain management. For example, a production accident or transportation delay for a key component supplier could stall production lines at the entire auto manufacturer.

Pressure of technological innovation: With the rapid development of new technologies such as the Internet of Things, big data and artificial intelligence in the field of logistics, automobile enterprises are facing the pressure of integrating these technologies into logistics process management. How to use the new technology to realize the real-time collection, analysis and decision-making optimization of logistics information, and improve the intelligent level of logistics operation, has become an urgent problem to be solved.

The contradiction between cost control and efficiency improvement: In the process of pursuing logistics efficiency improvement, more funds often need to be invested in logistics facility construction, technology upgrading and talent training, which is in conflict with the goal of cost control of enterprises. For example, although the construction of intelligent logistics warehouse can improve the efficiency of inventory management, the initial construction cost is high, and the continuous operation and maintenance investment requires [6].

Environmental protection and sustainable development requirements: the social attention to environmental protection is constantly increasing, and the logistics activities of automobile enterprises should also follow the principles of environmental protection and sustainable development. Reducing carbon emissions in the process of logistics and transportation, optimizing packaging materials to reduce waste, etc., have put forward new constraints and challenges to the logistics process management of enterprises [7].

Figure 1 The proportion of logistics cost composition of automobile enterprises

4. Development countermeasure

4.1 Countermeasures to the complexity of supply chain

Automobile enterprises should actively expand supplier resources and establish cooperative relations with multiple suppliers, especially for key components, so as to ensure that when one supplier has problems, it can quickly obtain resources from other alternative suppliers and maintain the continuity of production. For example, in addition to working with local suppliers, we can also establish strategic alliances with quality foreign suppliers to reduce the possibility of supply disruptions due to regional risks. At the same time, the supplier evaluation and grading system, regularly to the suppliers production capacity, supply stability, quality standards, etc. To conduct a comprehensive assessment, according to the evaluation results of supplier classification management, for good suppliers to give more cooperation opportunities and rewards, for risky suppliers response plan in advance or assist the improvement.

With the help of advanced information technology, the supply chain information platform is built to realize the real-time information sharing between automobile enterprises and suppliers. Suppliers can timely understand the production plan and inventory level of the enterprise, so as to reasonably arrange production and distribution. The enterprise can also grasp the production schedule and transportation status of suppliers in real time to warn potential risks. Through information sharing, the two parties can promote the cooperation in order processing, inventory management, logistics distribution and other links, such as jointly formulating replenishment plan and optimizing transportation routes, so as to improve the overall response speed and flexibility of the supply chain and reduce the supply chain risks caused by information asymmetry.

4.2 Countermeasure to resolve the pressure of technological innovation

Automobile enterprises should set up a special logistics technology research and development fund, and actively invest resources in the application research and development of new technologies such as the Internet of Things, big data and artificial intelligence in logistics process management. Cooperate with universities and scientific research institutions to jointly carry out relevant technology projects, and use external scientific research forces to enhance the technological innovation ability of enterprises. For example, the intelligent storage management system based on the Internet of Things is jointly developed, which realizes the real-time monitoring, automatic inventory and intelligent scheduling of inventory goods by installing a sensor network in the warehouse. At the same time, actively introduce mature logistics technology solutions, accelerate the application of new technology in the enterprise, improve the intelligent level of logistics operation.

In order to meet the needs of technological innovation, enterprises should pay attention to the training and introduction of logistics technical talents. On the

one hand, carry out internal training courses and learning exchange activities to train existing logistics staff for the Internet of Things, big data analysis and artificial intelligence algorithm to improve the technical literacy and application ability; on the other hand, formulate attractive recruitment policies, introduce high-end talents with rich logistics technology experience and innovation ability from outside, enrich the enterprise technology research and development team and provide talent guarantee for enterprise technological innovation. For example, we will provide generous salary and treatment, good career development space and rich scientific research resources to attract excellent logistics technical talents at home and abroad to join us.

4.3 Countermeasures to balance cost control and efficiency improvement

In the logistics process management, we should carry out the waste phenomenon in the logistics activities, and realize the balance between cost control and efficiency improvement. The logistics process is sorted out and analyzed in detail to identify the wasteful links such as excessive inventory, unreasonable transportation, too long waiting time and so on, and formulate targeted improvement measures. For example, optimize the warehouse layout to reduce the material handling distance and time; adopt joint distribution and recycling pickup to improve the vehicle loading rate and transportation efficiency; establish the pull logistics distribution mechanism to accurately distribute materials according to the production demand and reduce the inventory level. Through continuous development of lean logistics projects, gradually optimize logistics process and improve logistics efficiency without increasing too much cost input.

Automobile enterprises can actively explore innovative cooperation modes with logistics service providers, such as establishing a strategic partnership of risk sharing and benefit sharing. In terms of logistics facility construction, it jointly invests in the construction of intelligent logistics warehouses and logistics distribution centers with logistics enterprises, and shares the right to use and usufruct of the facilities according to the business needs and the ratio of resource investment of both parties, so as to reduce the capital pressure and operation risk of separate construction of enterprises. In terms of technology upgrading, both parties will jointly develop and apply new logistics technologies, and jointly bear the research and development costs and risks, and share the efficiency improvement and cost saving benefits brought by the technology after application. By innovating the cooperation mode, integrating the resource advantages of all parties, and effectively controlling the cost while improving the logistics efficiency.

4.4 Countermeasures to meet the requirements of environmental protection and sustainable development

In order to reduce carbon emissions, the logistics and transportation scheme should be optimized from the aspects of transportation mode selection and transportation route planning. Low-carbon transportation modes such as railway and water transport are preferred to replace road transportation. For long-distance and

large-scale parts and vehicle transportation, railway or water transport lines should be reasonably arranged to improve transportation efficiency and reduce carbon emissions. In road transportation, new energy vehicles are used to replace traditional fuel vehicles, and the proportion of new energy logistics vehicles is gradually increased. At the same time, big data analysis and intelligent transportation technology will be used to optimize transportation routes, avoid vehicle detour, congestion and other situations, reduce transportation mileage and energy consumption, and further reduce carbon emissions.

In the selection of packaging materials, biodegradable and recyclable environmentally friendly pack-

aging materials are used to replace the traditional plastic packaging to reduce the pollution of packaging waste to the environment. For example, the use of paper packaging materials or bio-based plastic packaging materials, and the optimization of the packaging design, to minimize the use of packaging materials under the premise of ensuring the packaging protection performance. Establish a packaging recycling system, cooperate with suppliers and logistics service providers, recycle, clean and recycle the recyclable packaging materials, reduce the packaging costs and realize the recycling of resources, and improve the environmental protection and sustainability of enterprise logistics activities.

Table 2

Logistics technology R & D input and benefit output

a particular year	research input (Wan Yuan)	Cost savings caused by the application of new technologies (ten thousand yuan)	Cost saving rate
2020	500	200	40%
2021	800	350	43.75%
2022	1200	550	45.83%
2023	1500 (expected)	700 (Estimated)	46.67% (expected)

Logistics process management of contemporary automobile enterprises is very important and faces many challenges. The complexity of the supply chain, the pressure of technological innovation, the contradiction between cost and efficiency, and the environmental protection requirements need to be dealt with urgently. To this end, enterprises can build a diversified supplier network, strengthen information sharing and coordination to deal with the supply chain problems; increase technology investment, cultivate talents to resolve innovation pressure; carry out lean logistics, explore innovative cooperation mode to balance cost and efficiency; optimize transportation scheme and implement green packaging to meet environmental protection needs. In short, automobile enterprises need to optimize logistics process management in a multi-pronged way in order to enhance competitiveness in the competition and achieve sustainable development.

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